

6TH INTERNATIONAL ETHICAL
HACKING CONFERENCE (EHACON)
2025

AI & Law

Kolkata, India

February 20-21, 2025

Organized by

Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence

In association with

Department of Law

University of Engineering and Management Kolkata

SOUVENIR

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From Editor's Corner

I have the honor of holding the position of Editor for the "**6th International Ethical Hacking Conference eHaCON 2025 - AI & Law**" souvenir, which is organized at the University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India on February 20 and 21, 2025. The main objective of this conference is to raise public awareness of cybercrimes that occur in the modern world and the legal steps that can be taken to prevent them. Keynote speeches and research paper presentations are given across four different tracks: the Evolution of AI, AI and Law, AI and Cyber Security, and AI

and Industry 6.0. Deep learning, machine learning, data analytics, intelligent systems, cyber physical systems, big data, rapid engineering, augmented intelligence, intellectual property rights, crime prevention, and cybercrimes are just a few of the study topics that have been explored in these courses. A forum for debate and idea sharing on a range of subjects, such as data privacy, deepfakes, blockchain, cryptography, penetration testing, cyber physical systems, digital twins, ethics, supply chain management, malware analysis, and risk management, has been established in an effort to build a secure society. Researchers from academia and industry, both domestically and internationally, participated in the discussions. Apart from research paper presentations, the conference hosted a series of events like **3MST** - Three-Minute Scholarly Thesis Presentation, **Dcyfr** – the coding competition on cybersecurity, **CTF** - Capture the Flag, cybersecurity competition for finding and exploiting vulnerabilities in a system, and workshops on AI and Law. The souvenir highlights every aspect of the conference in the hopes that, in the near future, fresh research findings may lead to the development of workable solutions for safe systems.

Dr. Mohuya Chakraborty

February 2025

eHaCON 2025

6th International Ethical Hacking Conference AI & Law

February 20-21, 2025

Souvenir

Organized by

Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence
In association with Department of Law

**University of Engineering and
Management Kolkata**

Message from Chief Patron

Welcome to the sixth edition of the eHaCON International Ethical Hacking Conference, held in 2025. The University of Engineering & Management's Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence in Kolkata, India, hosts eHaCON 2025 every year. Leading academic researchers and industry practitioners from India and beyond will have a forum to exchange their creative ideas, experiences, and state-of-the-art research in the fields of network security, ethical hacking, and cyber security. This is the primary goal of this premier event. Since the event is being held this year in collaboration with the university's Law Department and the Centre of Excellence in Cyber Physical Systems, it will cover a wide range of legal issues pertaining to cybersecurity.

The National Institute of Technical Teachers Training and Research, Kolkata, India; Notre Dame University, Australia; the Indian School of Ethical Hacking, India; Cisco, Sydney, New South Wales, Australia; Nanyang Technological University, Singapore; Congo University, Congo; and Ixonn Group, Australia have generously contributed to the technical sponsorship that has enabled eHaCON 2025. For this event's tremendous success, I would like to thank all of the sponsors, associates, supporters, and University of Engineering and Management members.

Prof. Banani Chakrabarti

Chancellor

University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India

February 2025

Message from Patrons

Welcome to the 6th International Ethical Hacking Conference: AI & Law, eHaCON 2025. The University of Engineering and Management's Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence hosts eHaCON 2025 every year. This year, the Department of Law has partnered. We express our profound appreciation to the eHaCON 2025 organizers for organizing such a fantastic event, where attendees from around the globe presented research papers on a range of topics, including AI and Cybersecurity, AI and Law, Evolution of AI, and Industry 6.0.

We are wishing the conference further success and motivation for the organizers' work. I hope this conference strengthens relationships and gives us all the tools we need to make a difference.

Dr. Sajal Dasgupta

Vice Chancellor

University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India

February 2025

Dr. Satyajit Chakrabarti

Pro Vice Chancellor

University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India

February 2025

Message from Conference General Chair

The Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence, in association with the Department of Law, University of Engineering & Management (UEM), Kolkata, hosted the 6th International Ethical Hacking Conference - Leveraging AI to Law on February 20–21, 2025, at the University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, New Town campus. It was a great pleasure to greet everyone who attended. The purpose of eHaCON 2025 was to provide a forum for free discussion on the implications of emerging technology for a safe society. Technical paper presentations, live demonstrations, workshops, a gaming competition, and an online hacking coding challenge were all well-balanced throughout the conference. The objective was to begin the process of completely automating cyber defense. During a two-day instructive research paper presentation and keynote address, the most significant new findings about computer network attacks and defenses, commercial security solutions, and practical real-world security experiences are given. Many nations from all over the world contribute research papers.

The keynote speakers, Dr. Ana Penteado from Notre Dame University in Australia, Dr. Althaf Marsoof from Nanyang Technological University in Singapore, Mr. Marcelo Bussacarini from Cisco in Australia, Dr. Gleuto Serafim from Ixonn Group in Australia, Dr. Shambhu Prasad Chakrabarty from India, and Dr. Souvik Mukherjee from India, have my deepest gratitude for their presentations on a variety of innovative legal, AI, and security issues in the digital world.

Dr. Shambhu Prasad Chakraborty organized the entire program flawlessly, for which I am incredibly thankful. To ensure the high calibre of the conference, very strict guidelines were followed to choose only the best technical papers from a vast number of submissions, with the assistance of a superb committee of national and international experts.

I am grateful to Dr. Sukanya Mukherjee and Prof. Sudip Kumar Palit for serving as reviewers of multiple papers. Additionally, I would like to thank Prof. Victor Nayak for his ongoing involvement in floor management and Prof. Shrabana Chattopadhyay for her excellent work conducting the technical programs. Prof. Pallabi Sengupta and Prof. Abhishake Roy deserve special recognition for their exceptional work compiling all of the abstracts for our souvenir. Prof. Abhisikta Basu did wonders in managing food and venue. Participants arrived from a variety of Indian and international schools, institutions, government agencies, and businesses. I hope the several events, such as 3MST, Dcrfr, CTF, and workshops on AI and law, were very beneficial to them.

I would like to express my gratitude to the University of Engineering & Management for co-sponsoring this conference and for their financial and infrastructural assistance. For their outstanding contribution, I am thankful to all of the academics and researchers from

Romania, Australia, India, Singapore, and the USA who serve on the advisory and technical committees. I also want to express my gratitude to the local organizing committee, rapporteurs, session chairmen, and co-chairs for their tireless efforts in making this conference a huge success.

Finally, but just as importantly, thanks to all of the writers and participants, Springer for technical help, and the University of Congo for technical collaboration. In addition to enjoying our culturally vibrant city of joy, Kolkata, I hope they had a good time at the conference!

Dr. Mohuya Chakraborty

Director

Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence

University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India

February 2025

Message from Convenor

On behalf of the Organizing Committee of eHaCON 2025 International Ethical Hacking Conference – AI and Law, it is my pleasure to welcome the attendees to the University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India.

The conference consists of 4 technical sessions with 42 contributed papers and six keynote addresses. eHaCON 2025 Program Committee, comprising distinguished members worked hard to organize the technical program. Following rigorous review process, out of about 295 submissions only 42 papers were accepted for presentation in the technical sessions.

Behind every successful event there lies the hard work, commitment and dedication of many personalities. Firstly, I wish to thank the entire program committee for the excellent job it did in organizing the technical sessions. Special thanks are due to all the reviewers for their obligation in reviewing the papers within a very short time. I am indebted to the faculty members of the university for managing the conference on cybersecurity and law where participants from various schools, colleges and industry, government officials are benefited. A special thank goes to the conference chair (Dr.) Mohuya Chakraborty for giving us immense support and encouragement throughout this period. Once again, I hope that all the delegates from India and abroad will find the program beneficial and will enjoy the historic city of joy – Kolkata.

I sincerely thank Late (Dr.) Satyajit Chakrabarti, Chancellor, (Dr.) Sajal Dasgupta, Vice-Chancellor and (Dr.) Satyajit Chakrabarti, Pro Vice-Chancellor of the University of Engineering & Management, for their constant support throughout the event. Last but not the least I thank all our delegates from various industries as well as academia for participation without whom the conference would not have been possible.

Dr. Shambhu Prasad Chakrabarty

Dean

Department of Law

University of Engineering & Management, Kolkata, India

February 2025

Programme Committee

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Mr. Marcelo Bussacarini, Cisco, Australia

Dr. Pabitra Mitra, IIT, Kharagpur, India

Dr. Mohuya Chakraborty, University of Engineering and Management, India

Dr. Rajiv Ganguly, University of Engineering and Management, India

Keynote Speakers

1. Dr. Gleuto Serafim, Director and Founder at Ixonn Group, Australia.

2. Dr. Souvik Mukherjee, India

3. Dr. Ana Penteado, Adjunct Associate Professor, Notre Dame University, Australia

4. Dr. Shambhu Prasad Chakrabarty, Dean of Law, University of Engineering and Management, Kolkata, India

5. Dr. Althaf Marsoof, Deputy Head and Assistant Professor of Law, Division of Business Law, College of Business, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore

6. Mr. Marcelo Bussacarini, Global Security Brand Strategist, CISCO, Sydney, New South Wales, Australia

7. Dr. Mohuya Chakraborty, Director, Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence (CCoE), University of Engineering and Management, Kolkata, India

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Keynote 2. AI and Blockchain Integration for dApp Development
Mohuya Chakraborty, Director, Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence. UEMK, India.

Keynote 3. AI-Driven Assessment of Carbon Storage Potential in Dominant Mangrove Species of Indian Sundarbans: Insights from Three Decades of Real-Time Data
Abhijit Mitra, Director (Research), Techno India University, India.

Keynote 4. Seeking the Deep Side of AI for Humanity: A View from The South
Ana Penteado, Adjunct Associate Professor, Notre Dame University, Australia and Shambhu Prasad Chakrabarty, Dean of Law, UEMK, India.

Keynote 5. AI and Cyberspace

Marcelo Bussacarini, Global Security Brand Strategist, CISCO, Sydney, New South Wales, Australia

Keynote 6. Artificial Intelligence and Legal Education

Althaf Marsoof, Deputy Head and Associate Professor of Law, Division of Business Law, College of Business, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore.

Keynote 7. Artificial Intelligence in the Republic of the Congo.

Pascal Sundi – University of Antwerp, Belgium.

Keynote 8. Shadow Victims: Revisiting Theories of Victimology in the Age of Digital Misinformation

Souvik Mukherjee, DUPR Scholar – HDR Candidate, School of Information Technology, Deakin University, Australia.

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Accepted Paper Abstracts

This section consists of the title, author names, and abstracts of the papers accepted for presentation at eHaCON 2025. The full papers will be reviewed for acceptance and published by Springer Nature book series "*Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*".

NFT ECOSYSTEM CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES: SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Paper id e-49

Abhilash Kayyidavazhiyil¹, Raja Muthalagu², Mohuya Chakraborty³

^{1&2}*Birla Institute of Technology and Science Pilani, Dubai Campus, United Arab Emirates*

³*Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence, Institute of Engineering & Management, University of Engineering and Management, Kolkata, India*

Abstract: *A non-fungible token (NFT) is a distinct digital identity is registered on a blockchain to verify ownership and legitimacy. Its inability to be duplicated, replaced, or divided makes NFT unique. In this study, the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) by Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) model of the NFT ecosystem, its challenges and opportunities are elaborately discussed. The novelty of the paper lies in the conduction of the SLR of the NFT ecosystem using the PRISMA model, whereby the benefits and drawbacks of the stakeholders of the system were analyzed and synthesized. The SLR started with 216 papers from various databases and ultimately selected 31 papers published during 2020-2024 that satisfied the selection criteria of the present study. The nine research questions and gaps in the current research trends have been identified with a focus on ethical analysis, market value prediction, security, smart contract, and use cases of NFT ecosystem. The study would enable future researchers to find many open issues of this new technology and to develop novel solutions to enable the NFT market to proceed smoothly.*

Keywords: *SLR, blockchain, NFT, PUF, smart contract, SCM, tokenomics..*

GENERATIVE AI TO BRIDGE THE GAP AND IMPROVE MEDICAL REPORTING INTERPRETATION

Paper id e-67

Trishita Ghosh¹, Sudeep Ghosh², Suparna Biswas³, Animesh kairi⁴, Soumen Ghosh⁵, Shekhar Maiti⁶

^{1,2,6}*Department of Information Technology, Guru Nanak Institute of Technology, Kolkata*

⁴*Department of Information Technology, IEM Salt Lake Campus, Kolkata*

⁵*Department of Information Technology Narula Institute of Technology, Kolkata*

³*Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Guru Nanak Institute of Technology, Kolkata*

Abstract: *The aim and scope of this “research paper” is to design an approach for medical report generation for patients using generative artificial intelligence (GAI). The main model used in this approach is based on holistic artificial intelligence in medicine (HAIM). The integration of generative artificial intelligence (GAI) in healthcare communication promises precise diagnoses, streamlined reporting, and efficient integration with electronic health records (EHRs), thereby revolutionizing patient care to create*

an advanced artificial intelligence system that can analyze medical data and produce comprehensive, easy reports for patients. Additionally, the system aims to prompt immediate precautionary measures, when necessary, facilitated by the GAI. This initiative seeks to improve communication between “healthcare providers” and “patients” by delivering clear and accessible information regarding their health status, diagnosis, and treatment plans. Ultimately, the project aimed to empower patients with clearer insights into their health, thereby fostering a more collaborative decision-making process. By leveraging AI technology, this endeavor represents a major advancement in healthcare communication, addressing the challenge of complex “medical reports” and enabling individuals to make informed health decisions. It also offers numerous advantages to patients, including improved accuracy, enhanced safety measures, and tailored insights for more effective health care management. Furthermore, proactive health maintenance is encouraged by delivering timely and actionable recommendations.

Keywords: *Generative artificial intelligence (GAI), Holistic artificial intelligence for medicine (HAIM), Electronic Health Record (EHRs), Pathology Education Informational Resource (PEIR), Artificial Intelligence (AI).*

ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHY BASED AUTISM DETECTION: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

Paper id e-68

Suparna Karmakar, Suparna Biswas, Nanda Dulal Jana, Aavek Chattopadhyaya, Bishal Sarkar

Guru Nanak Institute of Technology, Kolkata

Abstract: *Autism is a neuro developmental condition characterized by challenges in social communication and interaction, as well as restricted and repetitive behaviors. It is called a Autism "spectrum" disorder (ASD) because it affects individuals differently and to varying degrees. Some people with autism may have mild symptoms, while others may have more severe challenges. Individuals with autism may have difficulty in understanding social cues, maintaining eye contact, and engaging in reciprocal conversations and also may have difficulty with verbal and nonverbal communication. To diagnose ASD researchers have worked with Electroencephalography (EEG), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), genetic and socio demographic data. In this work we have reviewed the existing literature based on EEG for the diagnosis of ASD. EEG is a non-invasive technique used to record electrical activity in the brain. Small metal electrodes are placed on the scalp, and it detects electrical impulses generated by the firing of neurons in the brain. These impulses are then amplified and recorded, producing a visual representation of brain activity known as an EEG. It is commonly used in clinical settings to diagnose neurological disorders such as epilepsy, sleep disorders, and brain injuries. It's also used in research to study brain function. Here we have reviewed mainly EEG based machine learning approaches to detect the Autism. Future directions of research related to Autism are also mentioned.*

Keywords: *Autism spectrum disorder (ASD), Electroencephalography (EEG), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).*

META-TRANSACTIONS AS A SCALABLE AND OPTIMAL SOLUTION IN PUBLIC BLOCKCHAINS

Paper id e-78

Mohuya Chakraborty, Sudip Kumar Palit

Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence, Institute of Engineering & Management, University of Engineering and Management, Kolkata, India

Abstract: *Public blockchain networks typically require users to create accounts and pay transaction fees using cryptocurrencies to access services. These requirements can present challenges, especially for new users, due to the complexities of setting up wallets and managing cryptographic keys. Additionally, scalability concerns in public blockchains often result in network congestion and slower transaction times during peak usage. This paper introduces a solution designed using Solidity, enabling users to interact with the blockchain via meta-transactions without the need to create accounts or use cryptocurrencies for fees. Instead, users can pay fees in their local fiat currencies, which make blockchain services more accessible and scalable. By allowing multiple users to engage with the blockchain using fiat, this approach optimizes the system's scalability, facilitating a higher volume of transactions. We have implemented this solution on a blockchain platform to showcase its practical feasibility and effectiveness.*

Keywords: *Public Blockchain Networks, Solidity, Meta-Transactions, Cryptocurrencies, Fiat currencies.*

PERSONALITY PREDICTION THROUGH GRAPHOLOGY: LEVERAGING AI FOR ENHANCED RECRUITMENT SCREENING AND EMPLOYEE RETENTION

Paper id e-266

Ansh Chaudhary¹, Mohuya Chakraborty²

¹*Saratoga High School, California, USA*

²*Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence, Institute of Engineering & Management, University of Engineering and Management*

Abstract: *This paper investigates a novel approach to personality prediction through graphology, combined with artificial intelligence (AI), as a tool for improving recruitment processes and tackling high attrition rates in modern organizations. Using a dataset of 5130 handwritten samples from subjects aged 18 to 67, this study focuses on predicting the "Big Five" personality traits: Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Neuroticism, and Openness. A convolutional neural network (CNN) model trained on this data achieved an accuracy of 74%, showcasing the potential for precise personality analysis based on handwriting patterns. This AI-driven graphological analysis can serve as a preliminary screening tool in recruitment, particularly identifying candidates prone to Neuroticism, which may*

correlate with mental health concerns and higher turnover risk. The performance metrics for this class shows moderate precision (0.51), high recall (0.78), and reasonable F1-score of 0.62, which indicates that the model is moderately effective in distinguishing Neuroticism from other traits as desired. Candidates who demonstrate positive indicators in traits associated with workplace stability like Agreeableness, Extraversion and Openness having high precision of 0.94, 0.95, and 0.80 respectively and high specificity of 4.33, 9.18, and 5.63 respectively, are advanced in the hiring process. By integrating personality prediction into recruitment, organizations can better align new hires with role demands and organizational culture, fostering a workforce with higher engagement and resilience. The proposed approach addresses the critical challenges of employee retention and attrition, offering a proactive strategy for building a more stable, motivated, and cohesive workforce.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Graphology, Personality Traits, Employability, Recruitment, Convolutional Neural Network, Image Processing.*

DECHAIN: PRIVATE BLOCKCHAIN-BASED DIGITAL EVIDENCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Paper id e-118

**Mohuya Chakraborty, Sudip Kumar Palit, Debanjan Nag, Abhirup Bag, Pallabi Mondal,
Anupama Bain**

*Cybersecurity Centre of Excellence, Institute of Engineering & Management,
University of Engineering and Management*

Abstract: *This paper proposes a Private Blockchain enabled Digital Evidence Management System using Hyperledger Fabric and Composer to aid the activities of Law and Enforcement department. Applying the principles of decentralization and non-tamperability, the blockchain system guarantees proper registration, transfer and verification of all digital evidence at all stages of their usage. These processes enhance the transparency and security largely eliminating the vulnerabilities of the evidence succumbing to fiddling before the legal processes. By using smart contracts, the system captures activities like evidence registration, custody transfer, among others, plus integrity verification. It also enforces exclusive controls of participation for example, only police, investigators, technicians, or attorneys are allowed to engage with the evidence. This makes efforts of trying to manage the digital evidence require minimal intervention from human beings thus increasing efficiency. Performance trials show good system performance under 'live' mode. In general, registration of the digital evidence lasts 23.8 millisecond, transfer of the evidence takes 15.1 millisecond, verification requires 9.4 millisecond and generation of the reports requires 0.8 millisecond.*

Keywords: *Digital Evidence, Blockchain, Hyperledger Fabric, Hyperledger Composer, Smart Contracts.*

ANALYZING THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN SHAPING IMPULSIVE BUYING BEHAVIOR: A STUDY ON CONSUMER DECISION- MAKING IN THE ONLINE FASHION RETAIL SECTOR

Paper id e-223

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Abstract: *Online fashion business is flourishing and the use of various cutting-edge technologies is impacting consumer purchase behaviour. Impulse buying as we know involves spontaneous and unplanned purchases which is a common phenomenon across online shopping platforms. Most of the times, it is a result of a complicated mix of several factors. In the context of online fashion retail, our research aims to explore the factors that are driven by Artificial Intelligence (AI), and affects the impulsive buying habits of customers. The current study uses a quantitative method and a structured questionnaire to gather data from a group of different online fashion buyers. A regression analysis is performed to capture the impact of various factors such as personalized recommendations, virtual try-ons, advertising strategies, chatbots, and navigation ease in determining the impulse buying behaviour of online fashion shoppers. The study explores the mental processes behind impulsive decisions by analysing the interaction between consumer purchase decisions and different AI-driven stimuli. Various retail organizations can use the potential of AI technologies to make better marketing strategies and boost sales, while consumers become increasingly aware about how AI related technologies may affect their options for purchase.*

Keywords: *Impulse Buying Behavior, Online Fashion Retail, Consumer Decision-Making, Artificial Intelligence, Fashion Industry, Personalized Recommendations, Promotional Strategies.*

LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DIGITAL FORENSICS AND ITS LEGAL IMPLICATIONS

Paper id e-222

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Abstract: *The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Digital Forensics has revolutionized and reinstated the examination and analysis of both direct and indirect digital evidence, providing advanced speed of examination of report, improved accuracy of report and efficiency in getting the final result. AI-powered technologies can function within itself i.e. automate data extraction, pattern identification, and anomaly detection, allowing and aiding forensic experts to handle massive amounts of data more efficiently.*

Machine learning techniques helps in predictive analysis and real-time threat detection, therefore enhancing the identification of cybercrimes both in common and national level questioning and challenging the security of national importance. Nevertheless, the application of AI in digital forensics also generates substantial ethical and legal concerns. On the other hand, the implementation of AI also raises substantial issues, notably the possibility of algorithmic bias, the intricacy of AI decision-making while generating processed and available data, and difficulties guaranteeing the admissibility of evidence produced by AI in court which are further referred by experts. Concerns regarding data privacy and the possibility of over-surveillance are also raised by the use of AI in forensics. Furthermore, the legal system faces difficulties when it comes to who is responsible for mistakes produced by AI systems—developers, forensic specialists, or the technology itself. It is imperative to address these legal complications by refining regulatory norms, guaranteeing accountability, and encouraging both interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary cooperation and research outputs amongst engineers, forensic experts, legal experts, and legislators in order to fully realize the potential and possibility of AI in digital forensics.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI); Digital Forensics; Legal Implications; Machine Learning; Algorithmic Bias; Data Privacy.*

A DECENTRALIZED APPLICATION FOR SECURE AUTHENTICATION AND COMMUNICATION IN INDUSTRY 4.0 NETWORKS

Paper id e-115

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Abstract: *Industry 4.0 Networks are crucial to maximize profitability, optimize processes, and accelerate demand. Internet of Production (IoP) is the networked environment within Industry 4.0 paradigm, focusing on connecting production assets through advanced communication networks. In IoP, stakeholders can communicate with each other when required to share information about the products they send and receive in the supply chain. A secure authentication mechanism is required in this new concept to make safe communication, where stakeholders of a separate supply chain communicate with each other. This research paper presents a decentralized application (DApp) for stakeholders of the IoP. The proposed protocol provides tamper-resistant records, secured data transfer, and peer verification between stakeholders. The performance analysis of the proposed protocol shows its supremacy over three other related protocols under varied situations with a superiority score range of 50.84 to 454. The security analysis using the well-known tool Automated Validation of Internet Security Protocols and Applications (AVISPA) demonstrates that the offered scheme is free from replay and man-in-the-middle attacks. Performance analysis shows that it outperforms other related schemes.*

Keywords: *Decentralized Application (DAPP), Industry 4.0, Secure Authentication, Supply Chain Networks, Blockchain, Ethereum, Internet of Production.*

MACHINIZED MEDIATION: APPRISING THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN EXISTING DISPUTE RESOLUTION PARADIGM IN INDIA

Paper id e-134

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Abstract: *Artificial Intelligence has touched and transformed every aspect of human civilisation, including the dispute resolution scenario, which often is criticised for being inadequate and not justice-oriented due to bias or its cumbersome nature at the domestic level. Mediation against this backdrop, even though not a very new concept for the Indian legal system, its formal introduction through separate legislative enactments or special provisions being made for it has made it an inclusive dispute resolution model. It has brought some respite due to its “win-win” situation. Still, it has also been criticised for lack of proper skill or effective resolution, especially when an impasse paralyses this “win-win” model in India. In this context, introducing Artificial Intelligence (AI) creates a positive impact, especially when providing resolutions or helping with the nittygritty of the simple yet complicated mediation process. Still, again, the issues of lack of empathy and neutrality prevent experts from relying on AI-generated solutions or interventions. This issue becomes even more acute, especially when the laws on mediation are utterly silent on the scope of AI intervention and the validity of the AI-generated or AI-aided resolutions. The research paper examines this scope of AI intervention in the mediation process by analysing the stages at which it can be integrated to make it more robust. The paper shall also examine the legal challenges in using AI in the mediation process and how it is being done at the institutional level by the various private players offering mediation and ADR services by evaluating the model dispute resolution clauses and guidelines issued by these institutions.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Dispute Resolution System, Amicable settlement of disputes, mediation, mediator.*

ENHANCING INDIA'S ANTI-MONEY LAUNDERING FRAMEWORK: TRANSFORMING INTEGRATION OF EXPLAINABLE AI FOR BETTER TRANSPARENCY AND COMPLIANCE

Paper id e-138

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Abstract: *The case of Anti-money laundering (AML) is still a threat to the Indian financial system, overemphasizing the failure of the traditional AML approaches at the legislative, interpretability, and operational levels. Indeed, when financial institutions employ Artificial Intelligence (AI) in AML, its limited interpretability, whereby AI models act like ‘black boxes,’ creates a problem in comprehending the decisions made in AML. To mitigate this problem, this study proposes a research question: How can Explainable AI (XAI) be applied in the Indian regulatory environment to enhance model interpretability and decision explainability? This paper will focus on how XAI enhances the credibility and effectiveness of compliance and operations and provides valuable suggestions for institutional and policy adoption of accurate, explainable AI/ML systems into the Indian AML framework. XAI is an area of interest in understanding if it can make AI-driven models effective in AML, thus enjoying regulatory compliance in India. The rationale for doing so is that incorporating XAI will further enhance interpretability, decrease the prevalence of false positives, and increase the likelihood of compliance due to the improved observations regarding decision-making gained from integrating the former. This study develops an interpretability framework for examining India’s AML regulations derived from the Prevention of Money Laundering Act, 2002(The PML Act, 2002), The Reserve Bank of India (RBI), and the Financial Intelligence Unit-India (FIU-Ind).*

Keywords: *Anti-Money Laundering, Explainable AI, Compliance, Regulatory Frameworks.*

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE RIGHTS OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES: OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES AND THE FUTURE

Paper id e-141

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Abstract: *Technological development has attempted to help improve the lives of persons with disabilities. This Chapter will firstly attempt to analyze how Artificial Intelligence (AI) enabled tools and gadgets are helping persons with different kinds of disabilities. Nowadays, people with different types of disabilities have different platforms offering them AI based tools and applications tailored to suit their specific needs. In this context, various AI tools and gadgets suited to help persons with physical or neurological or psychiatric disabilities will be deliberated upon. Next, the Chapter will explore how AI helps in realizing the various rights of persons with disabilities as enumerated under different laws on disability like the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016 etc. AI has helped in realizing key fundamental rights of persons with disabilities – from the right to live with dignity to the right of non-discrimination to the freedom of movement. However, use of AI tools have sometimes posed as a challenge for these people too – like the over-reliance on AI based diagnostic tests to determine whether one is eligible for housing, or for some benefit under a disability scheme or the use of discriminatory AI based tests for job recruitment. In such context, this Chapter will delve into the negative impact of AI on persons with disabilities. Finally, the Chapter will look into whether with more and more advancement in AI, how the same can be used for the betterment of persons with disabilities.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, AI, Persons with Disabilities, Impairments, Right to live with dignity, Accessibility, Discrimination, Physical disabilities, Mental disabilities, Neurological disabilities, Reasonable accommodation, Personal mobility, AI and privacy, Data bias, Ethical concerns of AI.*

USE OF THE AUTONOMOUS WEAPON SYSTEM: EXPLORATION OF ITS LEGALITY IN NEXUS WITH INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW

Paper id e-155

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Abstract: *The widespread deployment of Autonomous Weapon Systems (AWS) in contemporary conflict presents numerous urgent legal and ethical dilemmas under International Humanitarian Law. This research article seeks to examine the legality of AWS under the current frameworks of International Humanitarian Law (IHL), particularly concerning the concepts of difference, proportionality, and necessity. Key research enquiries will encompass the compatibility of AWS with the fundamental tenets of IHL, any legal impediments associated with their deployment in armed conflict, and recommended regulatory measures to align such technologies with IHL. This research article aims to elucidate the principal legal ramifications associated with AWS, while considering recent academic discourse and prevailing international legal standards. The existing IHL will be evaluated only on its capacity to address the unique issues posed by the utilization of AWS, as indicated by relevant scholarly literature. Proposals for legal change and international collaboration aimed at placing AWS under competent governance, ensuring it is not perceived as a threat to the humanitarian standards governing armed conflict, will also be evaluated. This paper contributes to the ethical and legal discourse on autonomous warfare, advocating for a framework that upholds human dignity while adhering to IHL.*

Keywords: *Autonomous Weapon System, Use in War, Legality, International Humanitarian Law, Human Dignity.*

MOBILIZING AUTOMATED VEHICLES: HARMONIZING THE INTERSECTION OF TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND LEGAL REGULATIONS

Paper id e-165

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Abstract: *There will be significant shifts in transportation with the introduction of autonomous vehicles (AVs), which will increase efficiency, safety, and environmental friendliness. But these technologies can only be used to their full potential if technological breakthroughs are seamlessly integrated with strong legal regulations. The article delves into the ways in which technological advances and legal frameworks meet, highlighting how important regulatory measures are for ensuring the secure use of AVs. In addition, the article delves into the current legal framework around AVs, drawing attention to the difficulties caused by inconsistent regulations and the necessity for flexible rules that can stay up with the fast-paced advancements in technology. The purpose of this article is to examine current policies and case studies in order to shed light on how to effectively integrate technology advancements with legal requirements in order to create conditions that are favorable to the broad use of autonomous vehicles. The results highlight the need for manufacturers, lawmakers, and the general public to work together for the sake of society's safety and well-being during the shift to autonomous transportation.*

Keywords: *Automated Vehicle, Technological Innovation, Legal Regulation, Infrastructure, Policy Measures, Sustainability.*

PREDICTING THE FUTURE: THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION IN DUE DILIGENCE IN MERGERS AND ACQUISITIONS

Paper id e-182

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Abstract: *It is anticipated that artificial intelligence will substantially change the due diligence process for Mergers and Acquisitions. AI-powered solutions are continuously getting better in automating a variety of processes, including risk assessment data collection, and analysis. Investigating the public sources*

serves the initial stage in a due diligence procedure. At this point, AI can look for ongoing tax and legal conflicts in public sources including official announcements, financial reports, prospectuses, and media coverage. The problems found in such an AI-generated report might be used as personalised input for the management's due diligence information. By automatically categorising the submitted documents, AI systems can expedite the procedure. Additionally, the software could look for sensitive information in the documents. For transactions requiring numerous papers containing employee details, sensitive information, and intellectual property details, this feature offers significant time saving and efficiency benefits. After a potential risk has been identified, evaluating its impact of the risk follows. For this, people use "soft" information like their experience with identical situations, conversations with authorities and co-workers, practical training, as well as understanding of human reactions to legal and financial matters. In order to understand the patterns and control the risk assessments, AI can make use on its primary strength by identifying gaps and offering analysis of the submitted documents. This paper will discuss the effectiveness of AI in the due diligence procedure in Mergers and Acquisitions. The integration of AI in Mergers and Acquisitions is the future of due diligence and will make the entire merger process smoother.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, due diligence, mergers and acquisitions, risk, transactions.

'ASSIGNING LIABILITY FOR AI AND IOT DECISIONS': A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN 'STRICT AND SHARED LIABILITY' AS A REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

Paper id e-206

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things (IoT) combined has created its own unique ecosystem in the new techno-industrial revolution. The race between their exponential growth and regulatory attempts can be graphically represented as the difference between Geometric and Arithmetic growth progressions. Their seamless blend in our life shows the power these technologies hold over us. Mostly, they mean well, but a cocktail of legal issue arises when AI fails to act in a way that is expected. This is largely due to the core complexities of the differences that lie between product defects, opacity of AI decision making and algorithmic or data driven failures, exacerbated by the interconnectedness of AI and IoT devices, where failures may be due to external factors such as data breaches or network vulnerabilities rather than product defects. Most of these systems, being autonomous in nature and having the capacity to learn and evolve, becomes unpredictable, further complicating the assessment of potential harm and hampers the process of proving causation between multiple manufacturers, software developers and service providers, thus making assignment of liability a labyrinthine task and directly coming into conflict with 'Strict Liability,' which has been the cornerstone of consumer protection. This points towards its continuing viability, while making us consider if other concepts such as 'Shared Liability,' can be used to create a regulatory system, while fostering innovation and safeguarding consumer protection at the same time. This paper delves into the rigorous task of assessing whether the concept of 'Strict Liability,' can provide the necessary remedies in an integrated AI and IoT environment, while taking into consideration the alternative concept of 'Shared Liability.'

Keywords: *Strict Liability, AI regulation, IoT technologies, Autonomous decision making, Product liability, Legal frameworks.*

NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING OF HUMAN GENOMES: ETHICO-LEGAL CHALLENGES WITH REGARD TO DATA SECURITY

Paper id e-260

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Abstract: *Precision medicine is based on giving the correct treatment to the right patient at the right time. For appropriate treatment, it mainly looks for genomic information. By enabling the precise sequencing of many genes simultaneously, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technologies are potentially transforming medical practice. Although there is still much debate on the clinical efficacy, this technology is becoming more widespread in oncology. Modern artificial intelligence (AI), especially deep learning, holds promise for improving the accuracy of variant calling, improving variant prediction, and making electronic health record (EHR) systems in NGS-based diagnostics more user-friendly. The influence of NGS on cancer patients is examined in this research based on preliminary data. The present obstacles that prevent all patients with the genetic mutation associated with a particular therapy from receiving that therapy are also highlighted. Additionally, it examines the current level of AI in NGS-based genetics, emphasizing its limitations and potential future approaches. Lastly, the research focusses on the three primary ethical domains: informed consent, privacy, and outcome review.*

Keywords: *Next Generation Sequencing, Cancer patients, Privacy, Informed Consent.*

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LAW: NAVIGATING THE CONVERGENCE OF SUBSETS

Paper id e-270

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Abstract: *Recently, while OpenAI is facing lawsuits alleging infringements of intellectual property rights and privacy in multiple jurisdictions across the world, it simultaneously spotlights the ethical conundrums surrounding the intersection of artificial intelligence and law and underlying the shadow of technological advancement in legal frontiers. It is hence indispensable to appreciate the contours of such convergence at this juncture in order to assess whether the growth of artificial intelligence in legal sector satisfies the test*

of time and effectiveness. The present research article thus focuses on analyzing the bright sides and the challenges associated with the intersection of artificial intelligence and law.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, legal practice, judicial system, law enforcement, intellectual property rights, accountability.

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF LEGAL FRAMEWORK AND MARKET STRUCTURE FOR THE FUTURE OF VIRTUAL POWER PLANTS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN INDIA

Paper id e-96

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Abstract: *The energy industry is the one area of our life where environmental degradation is currently pushing us for paying closer attention to the adverse impacts of fossil fuels. Our centralised, ageing power grid lacks the resilience needed to resist the catastrophic weather-related occurrences that have become more frequent in recent years, as seen by the frequent scheduled and unplanned outages. Virtual power plants (VPPs) are leading creator of renewable energy initiatives. During moments of high demand and extreme weather, which are occurring more frequently, the conventional electricity grid is prone to failure. It is becoming more and more obvious that major infrastructure changes, including substation renovations, are needed for our electrical grid. As an alternative to such upgrades, VPPs have been effectively implemented, allowing for the deferral of some modifications while addressing others. Internationally, German business Sonnen produces a battery meant to meet 75% of a home's annual energy demand with energy from renewable sources while sharing the rest with the community at large in a VPP context. In the US, Tesla debuted Powerwalls in 2015. With the capacity to scale up to 1,000 assets, Central schweizerische Kraftwerke AG (CKW) in Switzerland developed a sizable VPP with 110 assets. This paper proposes use of Artificial Intelligence for prediction and Virtual power plants can offer users more economical power and a more affordable energy alternative and also proposes the legal and policy reform to build the infrastructure to promote competition in the market.*

Keywords: *Virtual Power Plant, Electricity Policy, Artificial Intelligence, Conventional Electricity*

SYMBIOSIS OF FOREST AND INDIGENOUS PEOPLE: A MICRO LEVEL ANALYSIS WITH AI INTEGRATION IN WEST BENGAL

Paper id e-286

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Abstract: *Forests, as invaluable natural resources, are a gift from nature that should be utilized equitably while safeguarding biodiversity for future generations. Indigenous communities are deeply connected to forests, relying on their resources for livelihood and sustenance. Their close relationship with the environment positions them as exemplary stewards, having conserved and managed forest resources through sustainable practices for generations. Agriculture, particularly shifting cultivation, and the collection of forest products such as timber, honey, wax, and fruits form the core of their subsistence and culture. However, with advancements in technology, artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool for managing natural resources, including forests. This paper explores the profound relationship between forests and indigenous communities and highlights the potential of AI in enhancing forest management. The study reveals a strong interdependence between indigenous people and forests while emphasizing the need to incorporate AI driven solutions for effective conservation and sustainable resource management.*

Keywords: *Indigenous people, Forest, Natural Resources, Utilization, Artificial Intelligence.*

THE DARK WEB'S INFLUENCE ON WEB TECHNOLOGIES AND SECURITY: INSIGHTS FROM THE INDO-CANADIAN MODEL FOR DEVELOPMENT AND CONTROL

Paper id e-267

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Abstract: *In the present regime of Internet utility and cyberspace, the Internet has a multifaceted classification, namely, the surface, deep, and dark webs. While the former two are comparatively easily accessible, the latter has quickly gained infamy in the media by virtue of providing enough anonymity to its users and proprietors to roll the ball for all illicit activities across the web. The contents of the same are not indexed by standard web search engines. Thereby the sale and transaction of certain data, goods and services that are prohibited from free circulation, has made the dark web an alluring hidden digital space which can only be accessed by using special technology herein referred to as the 'Dark Web'. The true picture of the aftermath of the data that the dark web houses, has rarely been a subject for scrutiny. Thus,*

certain gaping questions arise- Is the available data credible and beneficial? Is accessing the same legal? Can it jeopardize the functioning of the armed forces? These, and similar questions, have emerged to be even more challenging with several prominent cases of data re-identification coming to the forefront, raising the bigger question that whether someone can use the Dark Web to sell sensitive and classified information without any consequences. In addition to this, fake offers from scammers and other fraudulent schemes to cheat potential buyers are regularly getting added to the list. Such predators prowling around the Dark Web mostly go unrecognized and thus unreported. This research paper thus tries to create a review and thereby looks at the purposes as to the reasons for which the 'black market' of the world wide web- the dark web- is widely used for, with an emphasis on cybercrime, and how the law enforcement agencies play the role of its adversary, also providing a framework on policy recommendation within this nascent sector.

Keywords: *Online payments, Dark Web, Web Services, Covid-19, Security.*

NAVIGATING LEGAL AND ETHICAL CHALLENGES OF WEARABLE HEALTHCARE TECHNOLOGIES IN INDIA, USA, AND EU: A COMPARISON OF HEALTHCARE DATA SECURITY AND PRIVACY IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

Paper id e-253

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Abstract: *Treatment of patients has advanced with numerous technological innovations especially with the recent development of wearable health technologies. These trackable or non-trackable has been used in treating patients, given that it allows health practitioners to monitor and analyse a patient's health data from a distance using embedded sensors. Such devices trigger communication and prompt actions in real-time, which can help in delivering better healthcare. Despite the fact that this has enhanced the potential to shift healthcare mobility, it also leads to new ideas regarding the security of data and the privacy of the users. According to the FDA, wearable healthcare devices in the USA are regulated, which usually applies to higher risk medical devices and not to lower risk consumer devices. The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) regulation does protect a person's identifiable information but may not be applicable in full to some therapeutic wearable technologies, notably those which do not share or gather protected health information. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) offers health data as a subcategory which describes that it is highly protected and sits under the umbrella of the regulation. The concerned area in India is regulated by the Digital Personal Data Protection Act which defines health data as sensitive personal data – the category which requires degree of protection. The discussion examines the present stance on data security and privacy concerning the legal structure of wearable healthcare*

integration in different jurisdictions, namely India, USA. In addition, the potential threats and concerns such as data ownership, untrusted and unauthorised third-party access including misusing and tampering with health data, data reliability and accuracy, have been illuminated in this study. Furthermore, it focuses on data processing featuring the duration of data stored and the protocols on data sharing, storage, kept on questioning whether the data exchanged with the third party remains intact or deleted.

Keywords: Health Care, Wearable Devices, Personal Data, Data Security, Data Privacy.

POLICY INTERVENTIONS TO MITIGATE ACIDIFICATION IN COASTAL WATERS OF DIGHA

Paper id e-281

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Abstract: *The Digha coast, a prominent tourism hub in the maritime state of West Bengal, faces a growing challenge from acidification of its coastal waters. This phenomenon, primarily driven by anthropogenic factors like untreated wastewater from domestic sources, tourism units and shrimp farms, and industrial effluents, accelerates the corrosion of infrastructure critical to the local tourism economy. Seasonal variations in pH levels reveal significant fluctuations, with highest value in premonsoon (mean value = 8.28), followed by postmonsoon (mean value = 8.27), and monsoon (mean value = 8.24). Using a comprehensive dataset of more than three decades (1984-2022) spanning across three seasons (premonsoon, monsoon, and postmonsoon), this paper examines the impact of acidification on Digha's tourism units along with forecasting the scenario of aquatic pH in 2050. The paper also emphasizes policy interventions to combat the adverse impact of acidification. This study highlights the urgent need for strict enforcement of the Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) notifications to achieve ecological stability and sustain the economic viability of Digha's tourism sector. Recommendations include strengthening mangrove conservation, promoting sustainable waste management practices, and enhancing CRZ compliance.*

Keywords: Acidification; Digh coast; Tourism sector; Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ).

ADDRESSING CO2 EMISSIONS IN KOLKATA: POLICIES FOR SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS

Paper id e-280

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Abstract: *This study explores the alarming rise in atmospheric CO₂ levels in Kolkata, driven by urbanization, industrial activities, vehicular emissions, and inadequate waste management, with a focus on two distinct sites, namely Duttabagan and Barasat. Using more than three decades of real-time data (1984–2022) and the Neural Auto-Regressive (NAR) model, the research predicts a steeper rise in CO₂ levels in Duttabagan, attributed to its dense urbanization and commercial activities like presence of the biggest fish selling units in the megacity of Kolkata, compared to Barasat. The findings underscore the need for localized interventions, such as improved waste management, afforestation, and sustainable urban planning. Policies like India's National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC), the Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981, Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974, and the emission trading schemes are critical to addressing these challenges. Advanced technologies related to waste-to-energy systems are recommended to enhance emission reduction strategies. The study emphasizes the importance of public participation, effective governance, and targeted policies to curb emissions while ensuring economic and environmental sustainability, with the aim to position the megacity of Kolkata as a model for urban climate resilience.*

Keywords: *Kolkata city; Atmospheric CO₂ level; Auto-Regressive (NAR) model; National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC).*

POLICY-DRIVEN INSIGHTS ON THE IMPACT OF SALINITY ON BLUE ECONOMY IN THE INSHORE REGION OF BAY OF BENGAL: A STUDY FROM BALI ISLAND

Paper id e-278

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Abstract: *The blue economy, encompassing sustainable use of coastal and oceanic resources for economic growth, environmental health, and improved livelihoods, is critically influenced by salinity fluctuations of the marine and estuarine ecosystems. This research explores the impact of salinity on the blue economy in the inshore region of the Bay of Bengal, particularly focusing on the Bali Island sampling station located*

in the central sector of Indian Sundarbans. Surface water salinity data from 1984 to 2024 was collected during high tide, forming the basis of trend analysis and forecasting up to 2050 with an AI-based Neural Auto-Regressive (NAR) model. The study identifies potential adverse effects on infrastructure, tourism, and biodiversity. It also reviews the policy framework addressing salinity-related challenges, emphasizing the urgent need for adaptive strategies.

Keywords: *Blue economy; Indian Sundarbans; Salinity; Neural Auto-Regressive (NAR) model; Policy framework.*

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION IN LEGAL SYSTEM

Paper id e-126

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Abstract: *The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into the legal system is changing the landscape, creating both opportunities and challenges. In this paper, we explore the multifaceted impact of AI in law, starting with AI's role in shaping the future of legal practice. However, this technological advancement raises significant regulatory and legislative challenges, as existing frameworks struggle to accommodate AI's rapid evolution, necessitating new laws to govern its use. Furthermore, the Impact of AI on legal ethics and professional responsibility cannot be overlooked. As AI systems take over tasks traditionally performed by lawyers, ethical dilemmas around liability, privacy, and bias will arise, leading to a reassessment of professional standards. The impact on legal employment will be profound, as automation threatens some professional roles while creating new opportunities for technology-enabled legal practice. In addition, AI can promote the management and predictive analysis of the case and accelerate legal processes, so the judicial system and the judicial procedures are transformed. Finally, the integration of AI's legal education and training is essential and requires a curriculum for future lawyers. Overall, this paper delves into these consequences, providing a comprehensive analysis of the impact of AI on legal work and the legal profession at large.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Legal Practice, Legislative Challenges, Legal Ethics, Professional Responsibility, Legal Employment, Predictive Analysis, Judicial Procedure.*

AUTOMATED AI SYSTEMS FOR LEGAL COMPLIANCE MONITORING IN REGULATED INDUSTRIES

Paper id e-211

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Abstract: *The new AI-powered compliance monitoring systems use automated methods to review high-volume data to detect anomalies in operations and assess the risks of noncompliance to the lowest levels while meeting the high standards outlined in the legal environment. These preceding applications are especially critical in high and complex regulations. GE climates, such as finance, healthcare, and data privacy, are increasingly encumbered with complex and dynamically changing regulatory requirements, raising the cost of their compliance management. The findings reported herein investigate the architecture of AI-based compliance systems: data collection, natural language processing to identify keywords, and machine learning models to spot patterns and potential breaches. It also examines some of the challenges this faces, such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and lack of transparency, which is essential for standards of ethics and integrity within regulations. It also examined real-life applications and various case studies of AI in industries like finance and healthcare, as well as the efficacy and barriers that stand in the way of completely handling compliance. The study concludes the discussion on future directions by calling for advancements in Explainable AI-XAI, guidelines for ethics, and policy updates to rule on AI in compliance monitoring. Mapping out the potentials and limits of AI in regulatory compliance, this study communicates a roadmap for organizations and regulators on navigating responsible adoption, whereby AI would drive efficiency but maintain compliance across fast-shifting regulatory landscapes.*

Keywords: *Automated AI, legal compliance, regulated industries, anomaly detection, natural language processing, machine learning, data privacy, explainable AI, regulatory compliance, and financial compliance.*

IMPLEMENTING AI FOR ETHICAL HACKING: SAFEGUARDING CYBERSPACE THROUGH ADVANCED THREAT DETECTION AND DEFENCE MECHANISMS

Paper id e-45

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Abstract: *The research paper examines the evolving relationship between technology and life, focusing on the significant challenges led by advanced cyber-attacks in today's digital environment. While traditional*

cybersecurity methods are essential, they often inadequately address the complexities of contemporary threats. The study highlights the innovative application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in ethical hacking, emphasising its transformative potential for threat detection and defence strategies. The chapter specifically stated how AI, through machine learning and deep learning algorithms, can facilitate the early identification of cyber threats. It discusses AI-driven automated penetration testing, which enhances vulnerability assessments by simulating Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) and identifying weaknesses within systems and networks. The article recommends AI-enhanced defensive mechanisms, such as adaptive firewalls and real-time reaction systems, which counterpoise emerging threats. Furthermore, the authors investigate adversarial AI, questioning if hackers take advantage of AI technology and evaluating whether AI works for protection against such modern threats. Ethical considerations, legal frameworks, and the responsible application of AI in ethical hacking are inspected to ensure a balance between technological innovation and privacy. In conclusion, the authors evaluate the feasibility and understanding of adversarial AI, weighing the use of AI by hackers against its potential as a protective measure. This chapter provides critical insights into navigating the challenges posed by cutting-edge technologies in cybersecurity, advocating for a proactive and ethical approach to defend against emerging threats.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Ethical Hacking, Threat Detection, Adversarial AI Defense, Automated Penetration Testing.*

LEGAL AND REGULATORY CHALLENGES IN THE ADOPTION OF SMART CONTRACTS IN INDIA

Paper id e-277

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Abstract: *Smart contracts are easier, less time taking and hassle-free contracts without much intermediaries, however the scope of establishing liability puts up a debatable discussion were bringing in evidence for establishing accountability is a concern area. This paper tries to understand smart contracts from techno legal perspective. It tries to understand the payment mechanism, the nature of non-changeability or immutability of smart contracts and understanding the role of legal jurisprudence while dissecting and identifying legal gaps in grave attacks like that DAO attack.*

Keywords: *smart contracts, blockchain, cryptocurrencies, law, evidence, blockchain trilemma, DAO attack.*

NAVIGATING 'ACCOUNTABILITY ASYMMETRY' BY REASSESSING INDIVIDUAL CRIMINAL RESPONSIBILITY: GAGING THROUGH USAGE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DRIVEN AUTOMATED WEAPON SYSTEM

Paper id e-268

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Abstract: *Artificial Intelligence driven modern warfare have sparked significant debate regarding their use and the potential violations of International Law. The growing reliance on Artificial Intelligence-powered Automated Weapon System by states, coupled with their direct violations of various aspects of International Criminal Law presents numerous challenges. Despite their "automation," and "artificially" driven – the one who triggers or operates these systems, play an undeniable role in the outcomes. This creates a unique legal situation where the connection between key criminal law elements, mens rea (mental state) and actus reus (physical act), becomes difficult to establish. This leads to the major issue of an Accountability Asymmetry. Even though individuals are actively involved in the various stages of its manufacturing to deployment, AWS have been considered "beyond human control," resulting in a lack of accountability. As the use of AWS continues to grow and their complexities increase, it becomes challenging to assign responsibility to any single individual due to the various stages of operation and decision-making involved. While Article 25(4) of the Rome Statute clarifies that the International Criminal Court can only exercise jurisdiction over natural persons. This paper aims to explore this "Accountability Asymmetry" from the perspectives of Individual Criminal Liability.*

Keywords: *Criminal, AI, Law, Weapon.*

DUMPING OF WASTE IN WATER BODIES AS ENVIRONMENTAL CRIME: ROLE OF AI IN MONITORING, PREDICTING, AND PREVENTING VIOLATIONS OF ENVIRONMENTAL REGULATIONS

Paper id e-123

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Abstract: *Environment, encompassing air, water, land and living organisms, forms the essential foundation of life on Earth. Environment stands out to be the most important pillar supporting 8.2 billion (UNFPA) human life on earth. Human life is blessed to get the abundance of resources from the*

environment yet it faces unprecedented threats due to human activities. Such activities sometimes unknowingly or knowingly proceed to “environmental crimes”. Environmental crimes include illegal activities such as illegal trade of wildlife, unreported fishing, littering, oil spills etc. In this paper, the authors have focussed on the detrimental effect of illegal dumping near water bodies and how to combat this by integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) with our existing waste management systems. This paper deals with various Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms which can be used to detect, analyse, and predict patterns of illegal dumping near water bodies using multivariate datasets. Furthermore, authors of this paper advocate to leverage satellite imagery, surveillance videos and sensor data, to monitor and if possible, prevent illegal dumping. However, incorporating AI in our current legal systems comes with its challenges, the solutions to which are further explored in the paper.

Keywords: *Biodiversity, Environmental Crimes, Illegal Dumping, Legal frameworks, Artificial Intelligence (AI).*

TOWARDS GREEN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY- QUO VADIS

Paper id e-117

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Abstract: *In an era of growing need for sophisticated data analysis driven by varied Artificial Intelligence (AI) models, aggravated environmental impact also emerged as a serious concern as because the recent generative AI applications often require substantial computation resources to train large models which lead to increased energy consumption and carbon emission. Although AI is often believed to bring about solution to a plethora of environmental concerns, yet the current emission of carbon dioxide and large consumption of electricity by AI models is quite alarming. A study conducted in the University of Massachusetts has found that training an AI model can emit more than 283 kg of carbon dioxide. A more recent study has found that Large language models (LLMs), such as recently launched ChatGPT (with GPT -4) shall be consuming a substantial energy more than that of training GPT-3 on a database of 500 billion words which estimated to have required 1287 MWh of electricity and 10,000 computer chips. Standing at this juncture, serious environmental impacts from the exponentially growing disruptive technology has ushered a new parallel paradigm called Green Artificial Intelligence. Green AI, also known as sustainable or environmentally-friendly artificial intelligence, refers to AI technologies and practices designed to minimize environmental impact. The focus is on creating AI systems that are more energy-efficient, less resource-intensive, and contribute positively to environmental sustainability. Green AI is gaining traction in India as the country strives to balance rapid technological advancement with environmental sustainability. Several initiatives and applications of Green AI in India focus on reducing the energy consumption of AI technologies optimizing natural resources, and addressing environmental challenges. The paper therefore intends to advocate for a unified approach to innovation in AI focusing on integrated sustainability and ethics within AI technologies and focus upon the need for ecological balance, societal*

welfare and responsible innovation in aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals. Also, with the global regulations lagging behind innovation, the urgent need of the hour is to regulate AI innovations with an intense focus upon environmental factors and ecological sustainability. Besides, the paper also reflects upon how India focuses on reducing carbon footprints in order to address environmental challenges.

Keywords: Green AI, ecological sustainability, AI ethics, Zero Carbon footprints, Sustainable Development Goals, AI Regulations.

THE ROLE OF CONTRACTUAL ANALYSIS IN ADDRESSING AI-DRIVEN INEQUALITIES FOR PLATFORM GIG WORKERS

Paper id e-101

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Abstract: *The Fourth Industrial Revolution is characterized by rapid advancements in automation and artificial intelligence (AI), which are reshaping labour markets and significantly impacting platform gig workers. While the technologies such as platform economy offers great solutions their effectiveness depends on existing policies. The government plays a crucial role in establishing labour conditions and mediating relationships between employers and workers. However, inadequate regulatory involvement often leads to the perpetuation of informal and precarious work, leaving gig workers deprived of job security, benefits and fair wages. In this context, a contractual analysis of platform gig economy with the technologies reveals significant challenges faced by these workers under current contractual arrangements. The lack of adequate protections within these contracts allows exploitative practices to persist, rendering workers vulnerable with limited opportunities for skill development and career advancements. This highlights the critical need to examine the implications of contractual agreements on workers' rights in an AI driven labor landscape. Addressing the informal labour issues and improving skill development are essential for managing the effects of AI on employment; by scrutinizing the contracts governing the platform gig work, stakeholders can identify the weaknesses and advocate for stronger labour protection. This integrated approach ensures that the benefits of new technologies do not exacerbate existing inequalities, ultimately creating a more equitable environment for gig workers. The findings confirm the importance of contractual analysis as a tool to empower workers and safeguard their rights in the evolving platform gig economy.*

Keywords: *Fourth Industrial Revolution, Platform gig economy, contractual analysis, labour protection, AI and employment.*

ROLE OF AI IN TRANSFORMING MEDICAL INNOVATION: PATENTING AND MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES

Paper id e-145

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Abstract: *The intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and medical patents represents a burgeoning frontier with significant implications for healthcare innovation and intellectual property management. This paper explores how AI technologies are revolutionizing the landscape of medical patenting, enhancing both the creation and administration of patents in the biomedical sector. This paper initially examines the current state of medical patents, highlighting challenges such as the complexity of biomedical innovations and the increasing volume of patent applications. The integration of AI offers transformative solutions, including advanced data analytics for prior art searches, predictive modelling for patentability assessments, and automated drafting of patent documents. Through case studies, we illustrate how machine learning algorithms have successfully identified novel therapeutic targets and streamlined the patent application process, reducing time and costs for innovators. Additionally, the paper addresses the ethical and legal considerations surrounding AI-generated inventions and the implications for patent law. By harnessing AI's capabilities, stakeholders can accelerate the pace of medical breakthroughs while ensuring robust intellectual property protection. The paper examines future trends, potential barriers, and strategic recommendations for leveraging AI to foster sustainable innovation in the medical field.*

Keywords: *Fourth Industrial Revolution, Platform gig economy, contractual analysis, labour protection, AI and employment.*

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND TRIBAL KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS: EXPLORING PATHWAYS FOR PROTECTION WITHIN INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES OF INDIA AND BEYOND

Paper id e-288

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Research Fellow, Centre for Regulatory Studies, Governance and Public Policy, The West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences, Kolkata, India

Abstract: *The intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and medical patents represents a burgeoning frontier with significant implications for healthcare innovation and intellectual property management. This paper explores how AI technologies are revolutionising the landscape of medical patenting, enhancing both the creation and administration of patents in the biomedical sector. This paper initially examines the current state of medical patents, highlighting challenges such as the complexity of biomedical innovations*

and the increasing volume of patent applications. The integration of AI offers transformative solutions, including advanced data analytics for prior art searches, predictive modelling for patentability assessments, and automated drafting of patent documents. Through case studies, we illustrate how machine learning algorithms have successfully identified novel therapeutic targets and streamlined the patent application process, reducing time and costs for innovators. Additionally, the paper addresses the ethical and legal considerations surrounding AI-generated inventions and the implications for patent law. By harnessing AI's capabilities, stakeholders can accelerate the pace of medical breakthroughs while ensuring robust intellectual property protection. The paper examines future trends, potential barriers, and strategic recommendations for leveraging AI to foster sustainable innovation in the medical field.

Keywords: *Fourth Industrial Revolution, Platform gig economy, contractual analysis, labour protection, AI and employment.*

DEEPAKES: NAVIGATING ETHICAL CONCERNS AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

Paper id e-287

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Abstract: *The intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and medical patents represents a burgeoning frontier with significant implications for healthcare innovation and intellectual property management. This paper explores how AI technologies are revolutionising the landscape of medical patenting, enhancing both the creation and administration of patents in the biomedical sector. This paper initially examines the current state of medical patents, highlighting challenges such as the complexity of biomedical innovations and the increasing volume of patent applications. The integration of AI offers transformative solutions, including advanced data analytics for prior art searches, predictive modelling for patentability assessments, and automated drafting of patent documents. Through case studies, we illustrate how machine learning algorithms have successfully identified novel therapeutic targets and streamlined the patent application process, reducing time and costs for innovators. Additionally, the paper addresses the ethical and legal considerations surrounding AI-generated inventions and the implications for patent law. By harnessing AI's capabilities, stakeholders can accelerate the pace of medical breakthroughs while ensuring robust intellectual property protection. The paper examines future trends, potential barriers, and strategic recommendations for leveraging AI to foster sustainable innovation in the medical field.*

Keywords: *Fourth Industrial Revolution, Platform gig economy, contractual analysis, labour protection, AI and employment.*

AI TAILORED SAFFRON AND WHITE TERROR ON THE INTERNET- A STUDY OF RIGHT-WING EXTREMISM IN INDIA AND AMERICA

Paper id e-285

Surodeep Sanyal

JGLSW, O. P. Jindal Global University, India

Abstract: *The internet, envisioned by Tim Berners-Lee as a platform to unite families and foster global connections, has paradoxically evolved into a conduit for hate and extremism. This transformation highlights the challenges of balancing free speech with curbing online terrorism and extremist content. While nations like the USA, bound by the First Amendment, prioritize free speech, this approach has limited their ability to preemptively address threats posed by online manifestos of racial killers, as seen in incidents from Pittsburgh to Shanbagh. AI-based fact-checking tools remain ineffective due to potential biases and limitations. However, global responses such as New Zealand's "Christchurch Call" have demonstrated the potential for collaborative efforts by governments and tech companies to censor violent extremist content, exemplified by the swift action taken to remove the Christchurch massacre video. Conversely, countries like India, unencumbered by stringent free speech policies, have shown a growing inclination to regulate online extremism, as seen in cases like Bulli Bai and Sulli. These developments underline the urgent need for a balanced framework to monitor and mitigate online hate without compromising fundamental freedoms.*

Keywords: *Online extremism, Free speech, Terrorism and technology, Content moderation, Christchurch Call, Internet regulation.*

ETHICAL CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A COMPREHENSIVE EXPLORATION

Paper id e-290

Raghavan Krishnasamy Lakshmana Perumal¹ and Mohuya Chakraborty²

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Abstract: *This paper investigates the multifaceted ethical challenges and opportunities associated with artificial intelligence (AI). Drawing on key insights from existing literature, the study highlights critical ethical principles, including transparency, accountability, fairness, and privacy. Utilizing the PRISMA methodology, the research systematically synthesizes findings to address questions around ethical AI implementation and its gaps. The study identifies pressing concerns such as bias, regulatory inadequacies, and limited stakeholder collaboration while proposing actionable pathways for embedding ethics into AI*

development. The analysis underscores the importance of interdisciplinary approaches, continuous monitoring, and robust governance to ensure AI serves societal interests responsibly.

Keywords: *Ethics in AI, PRISMA methodology, fairness in AI, transparency in AI, AI in sectors, responsible AI.*

AI-DRIVEN ANALYSIS OF URBAN HEAT ISLANDS FOR SUSTAINABLE CITY PLANNING

Paper id e-178
Rahul Vadisetty

Wayne State University, USA

Abstract: *Due to the impact of Urban Heat Islands (UHIs) on local temperature, air quality, energy consumption, and public health, the issue is severe in the frame of sustainable urban development. This study presents an investigation into Artificial Intelligence's (AI) potential for analyzing and mitigating the effects of UHIs, with actionable insight into sustainable city planning. AI models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), using a wide variety of data ranging from satellite images, climate conditions, population density, and land cover classification, have localized UHI hotspots, analyzed various contributing factors, and simulated the efficiency of several mitigation strategies. The most critical correlations of UHI intensity with urban features-building density, vegetation cover, and material use are shown. The AI models effectively predict temperature fluctuations and quantify the effects mitigated by green infrastructure of green roofs and urban parks. These simulations support city planners in decision making at a prioritization level by cooling potential and informing data-driven sustainable urban policies. This study shows AI's potential in analyzing high-accuracy UHI and informing resilience strategies in urban areas. This paper describes how AI could improve the urban environment by underpinning sustainable urban planning and improving the quality of life of the urban population in the face of climatic changes. In contrast, most modern challenges related to data quality and computational demands are being addressed. The novelty here is provided through high-resolution UHI data analysis for data-driven sustainable urban policy. The results identify significant correlations of UHI intensity with features such as building density, vegetation cover, and material use. That showed the capability of AI to predict the fluctuation of temperature and to quantify the cooling effect from green infrastructure. It provides evidence-based recommendations for urban planners, focusing on AI-driven insights that will enhance urban resilience and improve the quality of life in the face of climate change.*

Keywords: *Urban Heat Islands, AI-driven analysis, sustainable city planning, convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks, green infrastructure, temperature forecasting, land cover classification.*

AUTOMATED AI-DRIVEN PHISHING DETECTION AND COUNTERMEASURES FOR ZERO-DAY PHISHING ATTACKS

Paper id e-221

Rahul Vadisetty¹ and Anand Polamarasetti²

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Abstract: *Among the most prevalent cyber threats, phishing attacks are still state-of-the-art and, thus, difficult to detect such as zero-day phishing attacks. Most of the conventional phishing detection mechanisms rely on signature-based or rule-based systems that cannot identify such new emerging threats and neutralize them in real-time. The paper proposes applying automated AI-driven approaches for detecting and responding to zero-day phishing attacks. Therefore, this research suggests developing a robust phishing attempts detection system, identifying phishing through diverse digital platforms such as emails, websites, and social media using advanced machine learning techniques that include but are not limited to NLP, image recognition, and anomaly detection. The proposed system will integrate supervised and unsupervised learning models within a framework that will deliver real-time countermeasures, including automated user alerts and blocking mechanisms. Experimental results are presented that evaluate the detection accuracy, false favorable rates, and speed of response by comparing performance with existing methods. These results show in detail how well the AI-driven approach reduces the success rate of zero-day phishing attacks and proves to be more adaptive and scalable than traditional methods. This research forms the basis for understanding the full potential of AI-based systems for cybersecurity defenses and resiliency while setting the ground for future developments in automated phishing counter-measurement research that may impact sensitive digital infrastructures.*

Keywords: *Zero-day phishing, AI-driven detection, cybersecurity, machine learning, phishing countermeasures, automated response, NLP, anomaly detection, real-time security, cyber threat mitigation.*

GENERATIVE AI FOR ADVANCED RECYCLING PROCESSES IN POLYETHYLENE AND POLYPROPYLENE MANUFACTURING

Paper id e-199

Rahul Vadisetty

Wayne State University, USA

Abstract: *Globally, artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionising industries, yet there are serious ethical questions raised by its quick uptake. Using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews*

and Meta-Analyses) methodology, this research presents a systematic literature review (SLR) investigating the ethics of AI application across many sectors. The review analyses the consequences of major ethical issues in industries like healthcare, education, finance, manufacturing, and public governance. These issues include fairness, transparency, accountability, privacy, and bias. This study attempts to identify gaps, provide solutions, and provide practical advice for guaranteeing ethical AI practices by synthesising the body of existing work. The results help academics, practitioners, and policymakers adopt more responsible AI systems by providing a thorough grasp of the ethical environment in AI.

Keywords: *Ethics in AI, PRISMA methodology, fairness in AI, transparency in AI, AI in sectors, responsible AI.*

PROTECTION OF 'CLIMATE REFUGEE': MITIGATION, ADAPTATION, PREPAREDNESS AND CHALLENGES, BY USAGE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Paper id e-292

Saheli Chakraborty & Nirbindu Banerjee

West Bengal National University of Juridical Sciences, Kolkata, India

Abstract: *Climate Change, which is largely construed as a 'scientific concept', has been a 'multiplier of threats' to human lives. Ironically, unprecedented damage caused by climate change has served as a catalyst for ongoing socioeconomic inequalities. The impact of climate change is not directly proportionate to the states or stakeholders that have been significant contributors to the environmental catastrophe. The adaptive and mitigating capabilities of certain states, due to their economic and technological advancement, have shielded them better from climate change. However, the states that have remained the lowest contributors to carbon emissions have largely been the victims in diverse capacities. Among the many severe impacts caused by climate change, displacement is perhaps the most devastating. Climate refugees—people forced to leave their homes due to climate change—find themselves caught in a double bind. When seeking asylum under Refugee Law, they are often denied recognition as refugees. Though International Environmental Law has started to address the connection between climate change and displacement, progress remains limited. As a mammoth number of people are anticipated to seek asylum as 'climate refugees' in a few decades, the policymakers, scholars and international organizations have been univocal on 'burden sharing' as the sole redressal to the impending global crisis that is engulfing several under-developed regions. In this context, artificial intelligence could be a tool in gauging the efficacy of burden sharing of climate refugees. Apart from predicting the migration pattern, system, network, and causal concern, AI may also be used by developed states to enhance the objective of determining refugee status in order to reduce the entry of such climate refugees. This paper analyses the role of Artificial Intelligence in the burden-sharing of climate refugees.*

Keywords: *Climate change, AI, mitigation, refugee.*

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Tentative Program Schedule

February 20, 2025 (IIT Research Park)		February 21, 2025 (UEMK)	
11:00 am	Inauguration	11:00 am	Keynote 5: Dr. Marcelo Bussacarini
11:45 am	Keynote 1: Dr. Gleuto Serafin	11:30 am	Keynote 6: Dr. Althaf Marsoof
12:15 pm	Keynote 2: Dr. Mohuya Chakraborty	12:00 am	Technical Session III - VI
12:45 pm	Keynote 3: Dr. Abhijit Mitra	1:30 pm	Lunch
1:30 pm	Lunch	2:30 pm	Keynote 7: Dr. Pascal Sundi
2:30 pm	Keynote 4: Dr. Ana Penteadó & Dr. Shambhu Prasad Chakrabarty	3:00 pm	Keynote 8: Dr. Souvik Mukherjee
3:00 pm	Technical Session I & II	3:30 pm	Valedictory

